

D1.6 Project Progress Report– Month 18

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Short Description	
Deliverable 1.6 summarises WILSON's progress during its first 18 months, highlighting the establishment of governance, monitoring, and RRI frameworks; definition of baselines and performance indicators; development of semantic, data, and interoperability frameworks; and creation of energy and non-energy digital twin solutions. The project is ready for pilot deployment and validation.	

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AEC	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
BMS	Building Management System
D	Deliverable
DBL	Digital Building Logbook
DMP	Data Management Plan
DT	Digital Twin
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EoL	End of Life
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load
IDS	International Data Space
IDS	Information Delivery Specification
INN	Innovation
IoT	Internet of Things
KG	Knowledge Graph
LBD	Linked Building Data
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
M	Month
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PDHs	Personalised Data Hubs
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
PMP	Project Management Plan
QMP	Quality Management Plan
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SLA	Service level agreement
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
UC	Use Case
UHI	Urban Heat Island
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

During its first 18 months of implementation (from 1st of May 2024 to 31st of October 2025), the WILSON project has successfully laid the strategic, managerial, and technological foundations required to achieve its long-term vision of enabling interoperable, federated, and data-driven digital twins for the sustainable management of buildings and districts. The period was characterised by the establishment of robust management and governance frameworks, the development of semantic and data architectures, and the consolidation of dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities that ensure visibility, accountability, and impact across Europe.

Under the leadership of CIRCE, Work Package 1 ensured the effective administrative, financial, and technical coordination of the consortium. A comprehensive governance structure, together with tailored management tools and monitoring mechanisms, enabled transparent decision-making and continuous alignment with project objectives. Furthermore, the Project and Data Management Plans ensured compliance with Horizon Europe requirements, FAIR principles, and GDPR regulations. Moreover, the Responsible Research and Innovation framework integrated ethical, gender, and open-science dimensions across all project processes.

The technical progress achieved during this period has been substantial. WP4 defined the baseline datasets, performance indicators, and use cases that underpin all subsequent developments. WP5 delivered the semantic and federated data framework, establishing the WILSON Data Space and Vocabulary Hub as key enablers of interoperability. WP7 developed the Personalised Data Hubs and blockchain-based governance mechanisms that operationalise data sovereignty and security. In parallel, WP9 advanced digital twin-enabled energy management solutions, including upgraded Building Management Systems, Digital Building Logbooks, and district-level optimisation tools, while WP11 introduced methodologies and tools for predictive maintenance, climate and biodiversity impact assessment, and risk and resilience evaluation. Together, these results represent a coherent and integrated technical foundation that bridges building-level intelligence with district-scale data federation.

In parallel, dissemination and exploitation efforts under WP16, led by INTRACT, established WILSON's visual identity, communication infrastructure, and European presence. The project achieved and often exceeded its quantitative targets, strengthening collaborations with over a dozen EU-funded projects and key platforms. These activities have significantly enhanced WILSON's visibility, positioning it as a recognised actor within the Built4People and Horizon Europe communities.

By Month 18, WILSON has demonstrated effective coordination, scientific excellence, and technological innovation, ensuring compliance, quality, and impact across all domains. With its governance mechanisms, semantic and data frameworks, and communication structures now fully operational, the project is well-positioned to advance toward its demonstration and validation phase, consolidating its role as a frontrunner in Europe's transition toward interoperable, human-centric, and sustainable digital twin ecosystems.

2. INTRODUCTION

This document constitutes Deliverable D1.6 – Project Progress Report (Month 18) of the WILSON project and provides a comprehensive overview of the project's progress during its first reporting period, covering Months 1 to 18 (i.e. from May 2024 to October 2025).

The main objective of this deliverable is to summarise the activities, achievements, and results accomplished during the period, assessing progress towards the objectives defined in the Grant Agreement and ensuring alignment with the WILSON implementation plan. The report compiles inputs from all partners and work packages, highlighting key outcomes, interdependencies, and management actions undertaken to ensure technical, financial, and administrative consistency throughout the consortium.

From its inception, WILSON has pursued the creation of federated, interoperable, and human-centric Digital Twin ecosystems to support sustainable, data-driven management of buildings and districts across Europe. The project is structured around complementary work packages addressing management and coordination (WP1), baseline assessment and performance indicators (WP4), semantic and data interoperability frameworks (WP5, WP7), lifecycle services for energy and non-energy uses (WP9, WP11), and dissemination, communication, and exploitation (WP16).

In summary, this report demonstrates that WILSON has achieved a strong level of maturity in both its organisational and technical dimensions during the first 18 months. All management and coordination mechanisms are fully operational, technical developments are progressing according to plan, and the dissemination and exploitation activities have positioned the project for broad impact and visibility at the European level.

Finally, it is worth explaining that the present deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** provides deliverable introduction.
- **Sections 3 to 9** present detailed summaries of technical, managerial, and communication activities undertaken during the reporting period, highlighting interrelations among work packages as well as the list of deliverables submitted.
- **Section 10** concludes with a synthesis of key achievements and an outlook for the next reporting period (M19–M36).

3. WPI – MANAGEMENT AND COORDINATION (I) (CIRCE, M1-M18)

3.1. Current Status and Brief Progress

The objective of WPI was to develop an effective administrative, financial, technical and legal management to warrant successful execution of WILSON. It ensured the achievement of all objectives in terms of time, quality and costs, setting appropriate management tools, and performing smooth and effective management and coordination of consortium guaranteeing joint understanding among partners.

WPI started with the project in May2024 (M1) and ended in October 2025 (M18).

Having above-mentioned objectives in mind, during the first 18 months, WPI successfully established the overall management, coordination, and governance framework for the WILSON project, ensuring smooth collaboration among partners and full compliance with Horizon Europe and consortium requirements. Activities were structured around four core tasks (T1.1–T1.4), each contributing to the effective implementation and monitoring of project progress.

In Task 1.1, CIRCE coordinated all technical, administrative, and financial management activities in line with the Grant and Consortium Agreements. A comprehensive **governance structure** (see Figure 1) was implemented to facilitate transparent and efficient decision-making.

Figure 1. WILSON Governance Structure

A dedicated **project intranet** on Microsoft Teams was deployed to centralize communication and document management. The *Project Management Plans* (D1.4 submitted at M2 and D1.5 at M19) established roles, responsibilities, inter-WP interactions, milestones, and risk-mitigation procedures, ensuring continuous alignment with project objectives and schedule.

In the framework of T1.2, a tailor-made **Monitoring Tool** was developed to track technical progress, deliverables, milestones, and workload distribution across partners. This system enabled systematic follow-up through monthly coordination meetings and biannual General Assemblies. Furthermore, by M12, an Interim Technical Report was prepared to coordinate the entire distribution of pre-financing and record the results obtained to date.

Figure 2. Kick-off Meeting of WILSON project hosted by CIRCE

Within Task 1.3, on the one hand, a standardized **quality assurance workflow** was prepared and applied to all deliverables, supported by internal review templates and validation procedures, to ensure that they are delivered on time and of high quality. On the other hand, **Data Management Plan (DMP)** was developed and maintained through its first and revised versions (D1.2 at M6 and D1.3 at M18), defining the consortium’s FAIR-compliant, GDPR-aligned approach to data governance. The DMP structured responsibilities for dataset handling, secure storage (SharePoint), and open-access publication via ZENODO. It also expanded the dataset classification into 11 categories, integrating pilot data and cross-WP interoperability measures thanks to the outcomes from task 4.4 (see section 4.1).

Finally, in task 1.4, WILSON’s Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework was initiated and formalized, addressing gender equality, open science, ethics, and stakeholder engagement. CIRCE led the establishment of the WILSON **ZENODO community** (see Figure 3), facilitated open-access dissemination of results, and initiated **gender-balance monitoring** and education activities. RRI principles were embedded across all project processes to ensure transparency, inclusivity, and societal responsibility.

The screenshot shows the ZENODO community page for 'WILSON: Distributed data modelling and Federated Digital Twinning for lifecycle data-driven sustainable operation and management of buildings and districts'. The page displays 3 results found, categorized by versions, access status, resource types, and file types. The results include 'WILSON_Roll-up', 'WILSON_Poster', and 'WILSON_Brochure', all uploaded on March 31, 2025.

Figure 3. WILSON community in ZENODO

Across all tasks, WPI provided the strategic and operational backbone for the project. It ensured coherent coordination among 16 partners, rigorous quality control, secure and FAIR data practices, and the ethical integration of research activities. With all management structures and monitoring mechanisms fully operational by Month 18, WPI has positioned WILSON for efficient progress into the development, integration, and demonstration phases in the next reporting period.

3.2. Deliverables submitted

Table 1. Deliverables submitted in WPI

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D1.1	Project handbook	CIRCE	31.07.2024	26.08.2024
D1.2	Data Management Plan – Month 6	CIRCE	31.10.2024	25.10.2024
D1.3	Data Management Plan – Month 18	CIRCE	31.10.2025	11.11.2025
D1.4	Project Management Plan – Month 2	CIRCE	30.06.2024	25.07.2024
D1.5	Project Management Plan – Month 18	CIRCE	31.10.2025	14.11.2025

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D1.6	Project Progress Report - Month 18	CIRCE	31.10.2025	20.11.2025
D1.7	RRI Report - Month 12	CIRCE	30.04.2025	29.04.2025

4. WP4 – BASELINE ASSESSMENT AND PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF BUILDINGS AND PORTFOLIOS (QUE, MI-M10)

4.1. Current Status and Brief Progress

WP4 aimed to: (1) document technical requirements for all tools, (2) define all UCs and KPIs to guide implementation, (3) identify data streams critical to WILSON’s objectives, and (4) evaluate the Pilots’ compatibility with these requirements.

WP4 commenced in M1 (May 2024) and concluded successfully in M11 (March 2025).

Task 4.1 aimed to identify **pilot assets, networks, systems, and solution developers’ requirements** to inform subsequent project phases. It involved analysing existing infrastructure and compiling technical, environmental, and socioeconomic data through collaboration with partners. Work was streamlined into three phases: (1) collecting pilot data via surveys, reactivated later to refine developers’ technical needs; (2) iterative analysis led by CIRCE to align innovations with pilot use cases; and (3) consolidating results into accessible formats for consortium-wide use. Deliverable D4.1 (submitted M11, March 2025) structured findings into methodology, baseline requirements, demo site descriptions, and gap analyses between developer needs and available data. The task established a shared knowledge base, enabling informed technical decisions and clarifying interdependencies between pilots and developers for upcoming milestones.

In T4.2, the focus was on defining **8 representative use cases** that align WILSON’s Digital Twin tools and business models with stakeholder and pilot needs. The purpose of these use cases is to translate complex requirements into clear, actionable frameworks to guide development and implementation.

Table 2. Summary of use cases, use case leaders and participants

Use cases	Name	UC Leader	Participant partners	Fronrunner pilot
UC1	Decentralised multi-source data management	TUE	CIRCE, UNEW, CSTB, QUE, PARQ, WATTX, IDSA	BAM
UC2	Energy monitoring and optimisation	CIRCE	SAK, CSTB, PARQ, WATTX	HMRIB
UC3	Data-driven network asset management	CIRCE	UNEW, CSTB, TUE, QUE, WATTX, IDSA	HSLU, SAK
UC4	Predictive maintenance	UNEW	CIRCE, CSTB, TUE, QUE, WATTX	BAM
UC5	Risk, resilience and biodiversity nexus	CSTB	CIRCE, RINA	ADD
UC6	Renovation planning and design	CSTB	CIRCE, TUE, RINA	ADD
UC7	Technoeconomic investment planning for property owners	GND	CIRCE, CSTB, PARQ, WATTX, UNEW	HMRIB

Use cases	Name	UC Leader	Participant partners	Frontrunner pilot
UC8	Boost of green energy investments by market actors	HSLU	CIRCE, WATTX	HSLU, SAK

On the other side, Task 4.3 focused on the technical development of the **BIM-SRI tool**, defining its core functionalities to enable an automated workflow for SRI score calculation. The key components include the creation of a custom IFC-to-SRI mapping framework, which ensures interoperability between IFC entities and SRI services while adhering to IDS and MVD standards. The development of the tool within this Task directly supports seamless integration with BIM processes and the WILSON data mesh approach. The tool’s architecture integrates dual rule-based and data-driven calculation engines to automate SRI assessments, alongside semantically structured data models that define input/output requirements for consistent results. To validate the tool’s applicability in WP13 and WP14, pilot baselines and reference levels are developed using national legislation and historical energy data, ensuring readiness of the tool for future evaluations.

As for T4.4, key activities included categorizing **WILSON’s data types**, developing a **DPIA plan** to address risks to sensitive or personal data, defining role-based access control requirements for governance, and establishing a maintenance strategy to ensure long-term data integrity and availability. The outcomes from this task were key to the developments carried out in the subsequent technical WPs, such as WP5, WP7 and WP9.

Finally, in Task 4.5, a **set of KPIs** will be defined to evaluate the innovation and effectiveness of WILSON solutions, assess pilot performance holistically, and benchmark WILSON technologies against competitor solutions and current demo-site conditions. These metrics will ensure measurable progress and competitive analysis.

4.2. Deliverables submitted

Table 3. Deliverables submitted in WP4

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D4.1	Detailed models of buildings at demonstration pilots	CIRCE	28.02.2025	21.03.2025
D4.2	WILSON use and business cases definition	UNEW	28.02.2025	21.03.2025
D4.3	BIM-to-SRI methodology and tool	QUE	28.02.2025	24.03.2025
D4.4	Data handling, management and protection	QUE	28.02.2025	24.03.2025
D4.5	WILSON KPIs life-cycle oriented indicators panel	RINA-C	28.02.2025	21.03.2025

5. WP5 – SEMANTIC AND FEDERATED DIGITAL TWINS AT LOCAL AND DISTRICT LEVELS (I) (UNEW, M6-M18)

5.1. Current Status and Brief Progress

The main objective of WP5 was to develop a framework for creating federated and semantic digital twins at both building and district levels, considering the adoption of existing ontologies and the WILSON data spaces architecture.

WP5 started in October 2024 (M6) and ended in October 2025 (M18).

In the first 18 months of the project, WP5 set the technical and semantic basis for WILSON's federated, sovereign data ecosystem connecting building- and district-level Digital Twins (DTs). Work advanced coherently across T5.1 Data Space, T5.2 Ontologies & Vocabulary Hub, T5.3 Semantic DTs (local), and T5.4 Federation (district), with continuous alignment to WP4 requirements and interfaces to PDHs (WP7) and tool integration (WP9-10).

In the framework of T5.1, the **WILSON Data Space** was designed and prototyped as the trusted, distributed backbone for secondary data use across pilots. The team adopted Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC), set out a hybrid access model (Data Space + PDH + direct API when justified), and defined the staging Data Space with core services (public connectors, Federated Catalog, Identity Hub, Issuer Service) for partner onboarding and iterative testing (see Figure 4). A structured connector development workflow and policy-based access/usage control were specified to ensure data sovereignty and FAIR compliance. These choices operationalise secure, contract-governed exchange between providers and consumers while preserving local control at pilot sites (see Figure 5).

Figure 4. Overall Data Flow Architecture with the main differentiation between primary and secondary data usage

Figure 5. Three cases for the deployment of connectors

In T5.2, the semantic interoperability baseline was established by surveying, comparing, and selecting well-adopted **ontologies** across WILSON data categories (BIM, BMS/IoT, geospatial, operations). The work prioritised reuse over reinvention and aligned with standardisation (ISO, CEN, ETSI, W3C, buildingSMART). The shortlisted set of ontologies (incl. IFC, BOT, BRICK, SAREF, SSN/SOSA, REC, GeoSPARQL, (Onto)CityGML) provides complementary coverage from materials/products to building systems and urban context. T5.2 also introduced the **Vocabulary Hub** to publish and govern controlled vocabularies/ontologies for both the Data Space and PDHs, enabling consistent mappings, versioning and discoverability across tools and pilots.

Table 4. Final selection of ontologies for use in the WILSON ecosystem.

Ontology	Domain Coverage	Alignment & Mapping	Documentation & Community
IFC	BIM/geometry	BOT, BRICK, SAREF	Extensive, maintained
BOT	Topology	IFC, BRICK	Active, lightweight
BRICK	Sensors/BAS	Haystack, IFC	ASHRAE, Growing, docs
SAREF (+extensions)	IoT/energy	SSN, BRICK, IFC	ETSI, standard
SSN/SOSA	Sensors	SAREF, BRICK	W3C, mature
BEO	Built elements	IFC, BOT	Wide adoption, mature
OntoCityGML	3D city model	IFC	OGC, mature
GeoSPARQL	Geospatial	CityGML	OGC, mature
FOG	BIM/Geometry	OMG	Wide adoption, mature
OMG	BIM/Geometry	BOT	Wide adoption, mature

Task 5.3 specified the **semantic DT framework** and minimum common DT model to harmonise heterogeneous pilot datasets while leaving room for pilot-specific extensions. The framework adopts a multi-layer semantic architecture (acquisition → integration/PDH

& Vocabulary Hub → semantic mediation → knowledge graphs → application/feedback) and defines a shared vocabulary covering District, Building, Space, System, Asset, Sensor, Observation, aligned with BOT, SSN/SOSA, SAREF, BRICK and IFC. The approach operationalises semantic mediation in PDHs and sets validation rules for data quality and interoperability, preparing tools (e.g., predictive maintenance, energy analytics) to query consistent, machine-interpretable graphs at building level. An initial application and gap analysis were performed for the UK pilot (Newcastle Helix) to demonstrate feasibility.

Finally, within T5.4, the federation principles and mechanisms that compose district-level DTs from distributed building twins via PDHs and the Data Space were defined, ensuring sovereignty-preserving, query-driven integration without centralising raw data. The task specified how distributed SPARQL/federated queries, shared ontologies (core + pilot extensions), and policy-enforced connectors enable cross-building reasoning (e.g., benchmarking, flexibility coordination, risk/resilience) while maintaining local governance. The resulting conceptual and technical design closes the loop from analytics to feedback/control, paving the way for TRL6/7 validations in pilots during RP2.

Across T5.1–T5.4, WP5 delivered interoperable interfaces with PDHs (data orchestration, semantic mediation), established governance and trust components for data exchange, and produced the semantic and architectural baselines required by downstream developments (WP6–WP10) and pilot validation (WP13–WP14). In RP2, work will focus on deploying the staging Data Space to pilots, publishing ontologies via the Vocabulary Hub, instantiating building DTs, and exercising federation at district level with WILSON tools, targeting measurable performance and interoperability outcomes.

5.2. Deliverables submitted

Table 5. Deliverables submitted in WP5

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D5.1	Data Space architecture and infrastructure	HSLU	31.10.2025	07.11.2025
D5.2	WILSON ontologies evaluation - Month 18	TUE	31.10.2025	05.11.2025
D5.3	Local and Federated district-level Digital Twins - Month 18	UNEW	31.10.2025	30.10.2025

6. WP7 – DATA INTEROPERABILITY FOR DATA MESH ENABLED DIGITAL TWINS (I) (TUE, M10 – M18)

6.1. Current Status and Brief Progress

The main objective of WP7 was to develop a service-oriented architecture that serves as a Building Operating System relying on (live) data connectors and transformers enabling access to heterogeneous data streams via Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs) of built assets.

WP7 started in February 2025 (M10) and ended in October 2025 (M18).

During the first reporting period, WP7 (Data interoperability for data mesh enabled digital twins (I)) focused on designing, developing, and validating the core technological components that enable secure, interoperable, and dataspace-ready data exchange across the WILSON pilots. The work has been organised through four complementary deliverables (i.e. D7.1 Personalised Data Hubs, D7.2 Blockchain-based decentralised P2P framework, D7.3 Connectors to legacy and third party systems, and D7.4 API software for data ingestion and system integration) which together establish the foundation of the project’s distributed data infrastructure.

In task 7.1, the **Personalised Data Hubs (PDHs)** were conceptually defined and prototyped to act as local gateways managing access, governance, and interoperability of pilot data assets. Their architecture aligns with the set of selected WILSON ontologies and the semantic models from WP5-6, ensuring harmonised data publication across sites. Figures below show two key features of PDH developed: key PDH criteria (Figure 6) and interaction between project tools and PDH (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Key PDH Criteria

Figure 7. Working interaction between any tool (for example, an LCA tool with connector logic) and the PDH.

Within T7.2, a **blockchain-based P2P framework** was designed to provide trust, transparency, and traceability within the WILSON dataspace. The first version is focused on modelling the interactions between stakeholders in order to validate the design and streamline the second phase of development.

In parallel, in the framework of T7.3, **connectors for legacy and third party systems** were developed to interface existing infrastructures (e.g. BMS, SCADA, IoT platforms) with the WILSON environment. These connectors standardise heterogeneous input formats (SQL, CSV, REST, MQTT, IFC) and transform them into harmonised data streams suitable for PDHs and analytics services. This deliverable has for now focused on making the overview of available legacy and third-party systems, as well as creating a number of the mentioned connectors, particularly including an IFC-based connector.

Finally, in T7.4, the **API and data ingestion stack** was implemented to expose sensor and operational data through a unified, read-only interface compatible with the Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC). The architecture includes:

- a secure HTTP Data Access Layer for federated access to relational databases;
- a Canonical Normalisation Service that maps diverse data sources into a common tuple format {sensorId, date, value}; and
- an Orchestration Framework (Apache Airflow) for automated data acquisition and aggregation workflows.

All components were developed, containerized, and tested within the CIRCE Living Lab, ensuring replicability and smooth deployment in pilot sites. The work achieved full technical alignment with the project’s federated data and semantic frameworks and established a robust, extensible baseline for WP8 pilot implementation in the second reporting period.

6.2. Deliverables submitted

Table 6. Deliverables submitted in WP7

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D7.1	Personalised Data Hubs - Month 18	TUE	31.10.2025	29.10.2025
D7.2	Blockchain-based decentralised P2P framework - Month 18	CIRCE	31.10.2025	27.10.2025
D7.3	Connectors to legacy and third party systems - Month 18	TUE	31.10.2025	29.10.2025
D7.4	API software for data ingestion and system integration - Month 18	CIRCE	31.10.2025	06.11.2025

7. WP9 – DIGITAL TWIN ENABLED LIFECYCLE DATA SOLUTIONS FOR ENERGY USES (I) (CIRCE, M10 – M18)

7.1. Current Status and Brief Progress

The goal of WP9 was to provide services to relevant stakeholders, particularly in the energy domain. This work package provided energy optimization services both at the building and the district level.

WP9 started in February 2025 (M10) and ended in October 2025 (M18).

During the first reporting period WP9 has advanced the development of digital twin-enabled solutions for the sustainable operation of buildings and districts. Collectively, these activities have delivered the foundational components that bridge building-level intelligence, data interoperability, and lifecycle data management within the WILSON federated data ecosystem.

On the one side, Task 9.1 delivered an **enhanced Building Management System (BMS)** architecture that integrates heterogeneous asset management systems (HVAC, lighting, metering, sensors) through a semantic, vendor-agnostic programming interface built on RESTful APIs and ontologies such as Brick, BOT, and SAREF. The upgraded BMS connects to the Personalised Data Hub (PDH), ensuring secure, decentralised data exchange aligned with the WILSON Data Space. It is available for connectivity with further downstream user interfaces (GUIs) in forthcoming work packages.

A key element of the strategy is the initial approach for implementing the **Digital Building Logbook (DBL)**. It is conceived as an RDF-based repository aligned with ISO 19650 and GDPR, designed to store lifecycle events, maintenance data, and asset updates in a machine-readable, auditable format. Together, these components provide a unified and traceable data framework that can support interoperability, transparency, and lifecycle optimisation across pilot buildings.

On the other side, in Task 9.2 the analytics layer for optimal building operation and occupant comfort were developed. Activities concentrated on CIRCE's Living Lab, where monitored systems and data pipelines were integrated to test predictive models for HVAC and lighting optimisation, combining comfort targets with energy efficiency

Building upon outputs from T9.2, in Task 9.3, the first functional prototype of the **Aggregated Demand Portfolio Manager (ADPM)** was delivered, operating at district scale. The ADPM performs rolling, price-aware and risk-aware coordination across multiple buildings using hourly demand envelopes, PV and price forecasts, and Monte Carlo estimation of overload probability at the Point of Common Coupling (PCC). The system generates hourly advisory setpoints for each building, prioritising grid protection, price response, and self-consumption. Pre-validation in CIRCE's Living Lab demonstrated significant improvements, confirming the feasibility of distributed optimisation using WILSON's federated data framework. Integration with the WILSON PDH and future Multi-Vector Energy Network Manager (MV-ENM) is planned for WP10 and WP13, progressing toward TRL6 demonstration.

Last but not least, within T9.4, the WILSON project developed the **Material Passport framework** using the **CONTINIUM tool** (INN7) digital twin platform. CONTINIUM acts as a centralised, semantically coherent data repository that supports building lifecycle data, integrates BIM/IFC models, and connects to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Biodiversity tools. This creates a unique decision-support environment for circular renovation, quantifying embodied carbon, biodiversity impact, and urban heat mitigation measures. The system’s ontology is compliant with *ISO 23386* and derived from *SAREF4City*, ensuring interoperability with EU Digital Product Passport initiatives. It provides KPIs for component mass, waste potential, and EPD-based impact, while allowing multi-scenario analysis (Baseline, AS-IS, TO-BE) integrating Nature-Based Solutions (NBS).

Figure 8. Overview of the scenarios and the role of the CONTINIUM solution

In summary, the first 18 months of WP9 have established a coherent, interoperable, and semantically governed foundation that transforms building and district management into an intelligent, data-driven ecosystem, positioning WILSON as a frontrunner in federated digital twinning for sustainable, lifecycle-based building operation.

7.2. Deliverables submitted

Table 7. Deliverables submitted in WP9

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D9.1	BMS upgrade and Digital Logbook - Month 18	TUE	31.10.2025	27.10.2025

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D9.2	Building energy use optimisation services - Month 18	CIRCE	31.10.2025	04.11.2025
D9.3	District-level and grid optimisation services - Month 18	CIRCE	31.10.2025	11.11.2025
D9.4	Material passports for sustainable renovations - Month 18	CSTB	31.10.2025	24.10.2025

8. WP11 – DIGITAL TWIN ENABLED LIFECYCLE DATA SOLUTIONS FOR NON-ENERGY USES (I) (CSTB, M10 – M18)

8.1. Current Status and Brief Progress

The WP11 objective was to develop the methodology for the building & district assessment by considering the impacts of various contributors (i.e. energy consumption, materials, equipment, water consumption, outdoor spaces, predictive maintenance and renovation actions) on the climate change, biodiversity, resilience and cost.

WP11 started in February 2025 (M10) and ended in October 2025 (M18)

During its first 8 months, WP11 established the methodological and technical framework for assessing non-energy uses within the WILSON data ecosystem. Activities focused on three main areas: predictive maintenance, climate and biodiversity impact assessment, and integration of risk, vulnerability, and life-cycle methods.

Task 11.1 developed the **CIMBA predictive maintenance tool**, which applies collective intelligence and transfer learning to predict the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of building assets. A prototype has been produced and initially validated at the UK pilot (Newcastle Helix), demonstrating improved reliability and cost efficiency for maintenance planning.

Task 11.2 defined the **HIBOU methodology (INN6)** for assessing climate and biodiversity impacts, integrating quantitative KPIs on environmental performance (climate change and biodiversity), and resilience (cf. UHI assessment in T11.3) at building and district levels.

Figure 9. HIBOU method (a) urban challenges addressed; (b) modules

Tasks 11.3 and 11.4 delivered the methodology for the **Risk & Resilience Assessment Tool (INN8)**, the models for the UHI assessment integrated in the HIBOU method and a framework

for coupling LCA/LCC with building management systems, enabling multi-criteria evaluation of renovation actions.

These achievements lay the foundation for the next phase (i.e. WP12), focused on integration, pilot validation, and operational deployment of the developed tools within the WILSON platform.

8.2. Deliverables submitted

Table 8. Deliverables submitted in WP11

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D11.1	CIMBA: predictive maintenance tool - Month 18	UNEW	31.10.2025	04.11.2025
D11.2	Methodology for climate & biodiversity impacts - Month 18	CSTB	31.10.2025	04.11.2025
D11.3	Risk and vulnerability & LCA/LCC integration - Month 18	CSTB	31.10.2025	03.11.2025

9. WP16 – DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EXPLOITATION (I) (INTRACT, M1 – M18)

9.1. Current Status and Brief Progress

The main objective of WP16 was to define and implement the initial dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities to ensure WILSON that work and outcomes effectively benefit built environment data management and reach the market. Furthermore, WP16 contributed to increase Project visibility and synergies between Horizon Europe supported actions.

WP16 started with the project in May2024 (M1) and ended in October 2025 (M18).

During the first period of the WILSON project, WP16 has delivered a coherent framework for project visibility, stakeholder engagement, and exploitation planning. The work was structured around three main tasks, achieving or exceeding its planned objectives for the period.

As for Task 16.1, this task established and implemented the project’s communication and dissemination plan. The strategy defined visual identity, messaging, and channels for targeted outreach, as detailed in Deliverable D16.1.

Figure 10. The selected WILSON Project logo

The [Project website](#), [LinkedIn profile](#), and press materials were launched early in the project, ensuring continuous visibility. By M18, all communication KPIs were met or surpassed: **3 newsletters** and **over 409 social-media posts** were issued, the website attracted increasing traffic, and project partners actively promoted WILSON during key events. The updated *Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan* (D16.2) reflected lessons learned and refined the monitoring framework to optimise audience reach and consistency across partner communications.

WILSON project aims to revolutionize data use in **buildings for improved efficiency, sustainability, and the creation of innovative services.**

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16 Partners
10 Countries
50% SMEs and Industries

Figure 11. WILSON project website (Main page)

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Figure 12. WILSON project website (Newsletter section)

On the other side, T16.2 achieved major progress in positioning WILSON within the broader Horizon Europe and Built4People ecosystems. As reported in deliverable D16.3, the consortium engaged with **15 related Horizon Europe projects**, exceeding the KPI of 12, and developed **13 active collaborations**. These included shared dissemination through newsletters and websites, joint session preparation for *Sustainable Places 2025*, and a forthcoming workshop with the STAR*track project. Partners participated in **11 European events and conferences** (target 8), including ENLIT 2024, EC3 2025, and the EGU General Assembly 2025, significantly enhancing the project’s profile. WILSON also established dialogue with **over a dozen European platforms and associations** (such as ECTP, DSSC,

REHVA, and the Building Digital Twin Association) resulting in tangible outcomes like WILSON’s inclusion in the ECTP project database and invitation to the BDTIC5 event.

In the framework of Task 16.3, foundational activities for exploitation were initiated in parallel with dissemination efforts. The consortium identified key exploitation assets, defined preliminary value propositions, and mapped potential uptake environments. Early collaborations with industrial and digital-twin communities, along with participation in data-space initiatives, support the alignment of WILSON outputs with European standards and market demand.

Figure 13. IPR Management Strategy for WILSON project

Last but not least, **7 peer-reviewed scientific publications and conference contributions** were produced in this period, reinforcing the project’s credibility and advancing its technical dissemination goals.

All in all, WP16 has delivered all scheduled outputs and exceeded most quantitative indicators established for the first reporting period. The project now benefits from a solid communication infrastructure, an active European network, and initial exploitation pathways that collectively maximise WILSON’s visibility and long-term impact. These achievements provide a strong foundation for the second period, where the focus will shift from awareness and networking toward sustained exploitation and policy-level engagement.

9.2. Deliverables submitted

Table 9. Deliverables submitted in WPI6

No.	Deliverable name	Leader	Submission date (planned)	Submission date (actual)
D16.1	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan & Execution Report - Month 4	INTRACT	31.08.2024	26.08.2024
D16.2	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan & Execution Report - Month 18	INTRACT	31.10.2025	21.10.2025
D16.3	Project synergies report - Month 18	INTRACT	31.10.2025	21.10.2025

10. CONCLUSIONS

The first 18 months of the WILSON project have been marked by strong progress across managerial, technical, and dissemination dimensions, ensuring a solid foundation for the project's second implementation phase. All planned activities under the first reporting period have been successfully completed, with deliverables submitted in line with the project schedule and objectives defined in the Grant Agreement.

From a management perspective, the consortium has demonstrated effective coordination and governance. WPI established a coherent management structure, efficient administrative and financial procedures, and a transparent decision-making framework that guarantees compliance with Horizon Europe requirements. The implementation of the Project Management Plans, Data Management Plans, and a tailor-made Monitoring Tool has ensured continuous alignment between technical progress, quality standards, and risk control mechanisms. The project has also integrated the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), embedding gender equality, ethics, and open science considerations into all processes.

On the technical side, WILSON has achieved significant milestones in the design and implementation of its federated and interoperable data ecosystem. WP4 established the baseline data architecture, performance indicators, and use cases essential for the integration of pilot sites and tool developers. WP5 and WP7 delivered the core components of the WILSON semantic and data frameworks, including the Data Space, Vocabulary Hub, and Personalised Data Hubs, which together enable secure, standardised, and sovereignty-preserving data exchange. WP9 and WPII advanced the implementation of energy and non-energy lifecycle services, creating functional prototypes of digital twin-enabled tools that address energy optimisation, predictive maintenance, and environmental impact assessment. Collectively, these results demonstrate the technical feasibility and scalability of the WILSON concept.

Dissemination and exploitation activities under WPI6 have further strengthened WILSON's European presence and strategic positioning. The project's visual identity, communication channels, and partnerships have resulted in high visibility and effective engagement with both the research community and key industrial stakeholders. Active collaborations with related Horizon Europe projects, industry platforms, and standardisation initiatives have created synergies that will enhance future impact and facilitate the uptake of WILSON results beyond the project's lifetime.

Overall, WILSON has achieved all expected objectives for its first reporting period. The project has demonstrated a high level of integration among work packages, partners, and technical components, setting the stage for the transition from conceptualisation and framework design to validation and demonstration. The outcomes of this period confirm the project's strong potential to deliver tangible contributions to Europe's digital transition in the built environment sector.

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